

Factors Contributing to the Incidents of Police Brutality in Bo City

Mohamed Yusuf¹, Ibrahim Munu², Sahr Adams³

¹Department of Peace and Development Studies, Njala University Bo Campus,

²Department of Sociology and Social Work, Njala University Bo Campus,

³School of Postgraduate Studies, Njala University Bo Campus

Abstract

The problem of police brutality is pervasive in police institutions worldwide, and Sierra Leone is no exception, as it exhibits similar tendencies. This research project investigates the incidents of police brutality in Bo City, Sierra Leone. The objectives of the study were to examine the nature and scope of police brutality incidents, identify the factors contributing to the incidents of police brutality, and propose strategies and recommendations for addressing and preventing police brutality within the municipality of Bo.

The research utilized a descriptive research design, incorporating a combination of quantitative and qualitative methodologies for data collection. A total of 101 respondents were the focus of the study, with a sample size of 81. The respondents were selected through a simple random sampling technique. Primary data was gathered through questionnaires Key Informant Interviews, and Focus Group Discussions. Quantitative data was analyzed using descriptive statistics displayed in figures, whereas qualitative data was categorized into themes for analysis and presented through narratives.

The results of the study demonstrated that the community of Bo City views police brutality as a major concern, leading to widespread unease among the populace. The study identified multiple manifestations of police brutality, ranging from torture and unlawful detention to corruption, intimidation, extrajudicial killings, protests, excessive use of force, and the use of chemical agents against crowds. Additionally, the research revealed that police brutality undermines peacebuilding endeavors by eroding public confidence in law enforcement agencies, diminishing their legitimacy and credibility, fueling social unrest, public outcry, protests, and demonstrations, all of which impede development and peacebuilding activities.

The study's findings and conclusions have led to several recommendations, which include enhancing the police training curriculum, establishing a reporting mechanism for unreasonable directives from superiors, prosecuting corrupt police officers, and implementing comprehensive reforms within the Sierra Leone Police institutions.

Keywords: Bo City, Police brutality, Law enforcement, Violence, Corruption, Peacebuilding

1. Introduction

In recent years, there has been a significant increase in cases of police brutality worldwide. This alarming trend has had a detrimental impact on the efforts to establish security and promote peacebuilding in fragile post-war nations, such as Sierra Leone. Throughout history, corruption, the excessive use of force, and various forms of unethical behavior have consistently hindered the progress and effectiveness of law enforcement agencies in almost every country. Developing nations, in particular, are more susceptible to these irregularities (Bayley and Robert, 2011).

The issue of police brutality in Sierra Leone has persisted for a significant period, characterized by the police force's adoption of a violent approach to law enforcement, which has unfortunately led to unnecessary loss of lives and violations of human rights (Kivoi, D. L., 2020). This prevailing violence can be attributed to various factors, including the force's establishment during the era of British colonial rule,

flawed recruitment policies, pervasive corruption, and a lack of accountability for the actions of police officers (Kivoi, D. L., 2020).

The occurrence of police brutality has the potential to undermine trust in institutions, exacerbate social tensions, and impede the establishment of sustainable peace. This is particularly evident in post-conflict states like Sierra Leone, where the pursuit of lasting peace is a delicate and complex endeavor. The excessive use of force by law enforcement officers not only violates human rights but also erodes trust in institutions and community relations, hindering the essential processes of reconciliation and healing that are crucial for the attainment of lasting peace.

In areas affected by post-conflict situations, particularly in Sierra Leone, and Bo City in particular, communities are already grappling with the consequences of violence and trauma. In such contexts, the presence of police brutality can exacerbate existing tensions and perpetuate cycles of conflict. This poses a significant challenge to the establishment of trust and social cohesion, which are essential for effective peacebuilding. It is within this challenging reality that this study sought to explore the incidents of police brutality in Bo City, Sierra Leone.

2. The Prevalence of Police Brutality in Sierra Leone

The United Nations (1979) defines police brutality as a serious criminal offense and a violation of fundamental and constitutional rights. This transpires when law enforcement officers utilize excessive force in their interactions with civilians, going beyond what is considered necessary (Snyman, 2008). Police brutality can take on various forms, ranging from minor misconduct necessitating administrative responses to severe transgressions requiring both disciplinary measures and criminal prosecution of the officers implicated.

Police brutality remains a significant concern in Sierra Leone, as numerous cases of excessive force and violence have been reported throughout the country, including in Bo. The aggressive actions of law enforcement officers have resulted in the tragic loss of innocent lives, caused injuries, and property damage, particularly during protests and demonstrations. Notably, in 2007, the Sierra Leone Police were responsible for the fatal shooting of several individuals in Koidu Town, prompting widespread criticism of the government's response to the incident (Awareness Times, 2007). Subsequently, in 2012, police officers in Kono District resorted to excessive force against protesters, resulting in the deaths of at least two individuals (Awareness Times, 2007). The events of 2016 in Kabala, where two individuals were fatally shot during protests, further underscored the pervasive issue of police brutality in Sierra Leone (Awareness Times, 2007).

In Bo City, the situation is no different. In 2011, the All Peoples Congress' office was stoned and set on fire by a group from the Sierra Leone Peoples Party during a procession, leading to the arrest of several suspects (ACHPR, 2022). The same year, an OSD personnel attached to the Bo Police Division shot a bike rider along MaheiBoima Road, Bo City, who was later pronounced dead at the Bo Government Hospital (Sierra Herald, 2017). The situation in Bo City has been characterized by major and consistent security lapses, with the Bo Police Division being criticized for underestimating the operations and failing to put in place proper security measures (ACHPR, 2022).

In 2017, police in Sierra Leone reportedly discharged firearms at protesting students, resulting in one fatality and other injuries in Bo (Akwei, 2008). Students at Njala University protested against their lecturers' continued industrial action, which commenced in October 2016, due to the government's failure to pay salaries for months (Akwei, 2008). Amnesty International denounced the police's actions, characterizing them as a tragedy and an excessive response (Akwei, 2008). The police stated that the students had not secured permission before conducting the protest, which led to the incineration of tires and the blocking of significant transportation routes (Akwei, 2008).

The prevalence of police brutality in Sierra Leone is an issue that is widespread and affects many countries in Africa. The use of excessive force by security forces during protests has been a recurring theme in Sierra Leone, and consistent security lapses have characterized the situation in Bo City.

The respondents were required to evaluate their thoughts on the concept of police brutality. The outcomes of the study are visually showcased in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Respondent’s Description of the Concept of Police Brutality

Source: The Research Findings (June, 2024)

The results from the investigation outlined in Figure 1 reveal that a significant majority of the respondents, 27 (33.3%), perceive police brutality as the disproportionate use of force resulting in severe physical harm, injury, or fatalities. In contrast, 11 (13.6%) of the participants view police brutality as the excessive use of force by law enforcement officers against civilians, while another 11 (13.6%) identify it as the abuse of power and authority by these officers. Moreover, 8 (9.9%) of the respondents describe police brutality as actions that infringe upon individuals' civil rights and freedoms. Additionally, 7 (8.6%) of the research subjects categorize police brutality as the use of excessive force that surpasses what is necessary for public safety. Furthermore, 6 (7.4%) of the participants view police brutality as the breakdown of trust between law enforcement and communities due to abusive behaviors. Similarly, 6 (7.4%) of the study sample highlight police brutality as unjustified arrests and detentions without legal basis. The remaining 5 (6.2%) of the respondents define police brutality as unwarranted violence, discrimination, and intimidation against civilians. These findings collectively indicate that police brutality involves the disproportionate use of force resulting in severe physical harm, injury, or fatalities. This conclusion aligns with Mack's (2023) research, which characterizes police brutality as the unwarranted and/or excessive use of force by police officers, leading to serious injuries, deaths, and a breakdown in trust between law enforcement and the public.

3. Literature Review on Police Brutality

The current social dilemma causing widespread panic and distress among citizens worldwide is the issue of police brutality toward the very individuals they are supposed to serve. The police institution was originally established to maintain security and order within society, ensuring that justice and equality prevail while

enforcing the law. Nevertheless, when the institution tasked with protecting the people ends up instilling fear, and insecurity, and perpetrating violence against them, it embodies the worst forms of oppression and disloyalty. Such actions not only violate the constitution of Sierra Leone but also contravene international human rights norms (Moore, 2024).

The concept of police brutality is multifaceted and intricate, encapsulating the excessive and unjustified use of force by police personnel toward individuals or groups, often leading to physical harm or even loss of life (Gale, 2023). This type of police misconduct constitutes a grave violation of civil rights and can take different forms, such as physical assaults, firearm discharge incidents, improper takedown procedures, and the unwarranted usage of conductive energy devices (Ryan J. Gallagher, et al., 2023).

In a publication released by Amnesty International (2014), it was identified that police brutality and the excessive use of force by law enforcement officers can be legally classified as a violation of civil rights. This occurs when law enforcement individuals administer an unjustifiably high level of force against an individual. Moreover, certain countries' police forces are plagued by significant deficiencies, with instances of using torture as an interrogation technique and perpetrating various other grave human rights abuses. Consequently, these violations have garnered substantial public scrutiny, disfavor, and condemnation of the police forces in question (Amnesty International, 2014; Aborisade&Fayemi, 2015).

The term "police brutality" was initially coined in Britain during the mid-19th century and subsequently gained attention in the American press in 1872. This timeframe highlights the enduring nature of this social problem, which can be traced back to the 18th century. Historical evidence suggests that early instances of police brutality in the United States were often associated with labor strikes, marking the beginning of widespread occurrences. As time progressed, the concept evolved, expanding its scope to encompass various forms of mistreatment, such as harassment, intimidation, and verbal abuse, in addition to other acts (Gale, 2023).

In his study, Onyango (2018) brings attention to the troubling reality that the police force often demands bribes in exchange for providing necessary services. However, the situation deteriorates further as the political elites and influential individuals within society engage in corrupt practices, leading to the police harassing and brutally treating the very citizens they are supposed to protect. Onyango explains that such misconducts by the police are not isolated incidents but are rather intertwined with external organizational elements, resembling cartel-like enterprises that exploit the complex interplay between institutional and environmental factors in the realm of law enforcement (Onyango, 2018).

Police brutality has become a pressing issue in numerous countries around the world. The routine use of excessive force by law enforcement has resulted in numerous cases of unwarranted harm and suffering inflicted upon civilians. This concerning pattern has prompted widespread attention from the media, government bodies, and the general public globally. In a study by Thompson and Lee (2004), police brutality encompasses the unjustified use of force by officers in their interactions with individuals. This can take various forms, including assault, harassment, intimidation, verbal abuse, false arrest, sexual abuse, or repression. The brutality can manifest in physical forms, such as direct physical harm, or nonphysical forms, such as the use of derogatory language (Thompson and Lee, 2004).

Police brutality in the United States often intersects with race, leading to a disproportionate impact on people of color. The death of George Floyd, a 46-year-old black man, on May 25, 2020, in Minneapolis, Minnesota, as a result of a police officer kneeling on his neck for nearly nine minutes, triggered widespread protests nationwide and globally, urging for the accountability of the involved officers and fundamental changes in policing methods (Amnesty International, 2024).

Furthermore, it is important to note that in the United States, the majority of deaths caused by police officers are a direct result of the use of firearms. In numerous instances, officers have been found to have fired multiple shots at individuals, indicating an excessive and disproportionate use of force. A prime example of this is the case of Michael Brown, an unarmed individual who was shot a total of six times. A

comprehensive report on the prevalence of police violence in the United States (2019) revealed that black individuals accounted for 24% of those killed by the police, despite comprising only 13% of the population (Amnesty International, 2024). Extensive scholarly research has consistently highlighted the existence of significant racial disparities in cases of police brutality within the United States, with multiple studies concluding that black individuals are frequently subjected to excessive and deadly force by law enforcement agencies (Desmond et al., 2016).

In the city of Moscow, Russia, a similar scenario unfolds. The prevailing issue of police brutality persists, casting a dark shadow over the region. Numerous instances of documented police brutality in Russia serve as evidence, highlighting the prevalence of predatory policing. This form of policing involves the exploitation of authority by the police for personal gain or to serve the interests of the ruling elites. Consequently, the fight against crime takes a backseat, becoming a peripheral concern (Gerber & Mendelson, 2008).

Police brutality in Europe, particularly in France, Britain, and Germany, has given rise to significant concerns regarding the treatment of racial minorities and the application of force by law enforcement authorities. In France, enduring issues have emerged with police targeting and mistreating black and Arab individuals, resulting in widespread demonstrations and allegations of discriminatory behaviors (Amnesty International, 2024). The Gangs Matrix in the UK has faced criticism for disproportionately singling out young black men, leading to stigmatization and challenges in various aspects of life for those categorized as suspected gang members (Amnesty International, 2024).

Police brutality is a pervasive issue that affects individuals and communities across the globe, including Africa. The origins of police brutality can be traced back to the era of slavery and the implementation of oppressive policies like the Jim Crow laws (Hannah LF Cooper, 2015). In Africa, police brutality has been linked to the militarization of police departments and the treatment of civilians as enemies rather than the individuals they are charged to protect. This perspective can lead to aggressive police and civilian interactions, increasing the chances of violence occurring (Hannah LF Cooper, 2015). Abdelmottlep(2016) identifies Sudan, Nigeria, Kenya, and Uganda as the African nations with the highest rates of police brutality.

In Sudan, Mahmoud (2019) detailed incidents of state-sanctioned attacks on medical staff by the police. The government's systematic targeting of doctors in Sudan has been a longstanding practice and not an isolated event. Since the outbreak of civil unrest in December 2018, medical professionals have been victims of police brutality, as they have treated individuals injured by live ammunition and violent assaults by police and NISS agents. The recent deaths of Dr. Babiker Abdel Hamid and MahjoubEltaj underscore the risks faced by healthcare workers in Sudan, with numerous others currently held in unsanitary conditions (Mahmoud, 2019).

In a study by Ariho (2019), the Police Force in Uganda is a semi-autonomous institution that was established by the 1995 Constitution as a key agency responsible for safeguarding and promoting the rights of the people. Despite this mandate, it has been found that the police force has been one of the main violators of fundamental rights, particularly the right to life. The research also revealed that from 1995 to 2018, the right to life was consistently one of the most violated rights by the Uganda Police Force (Ariho, 2019). Recently, BBC reported a story of the Ugandan opposition Leader Bobby Wine been shot by a police officer outside Kampala.

The problem with the use of excessive force by the police is a security challenge for Africa. In Nigeria, it has become a significant focal point, marked by reports of disorder, torture, extrajudicial killings, physical assault, and the abuse of power by law enforcement personnel (Chukwu et al., 2020). It has been suggested that the prolonged military presence in governance has influenced the conduct of the police force towards human rights violations, fostering a climate of exploitation and brutality rather than protection. The widespread prevalence of police brutality in Nigeria has deeply affected the mental state of Nigerians, as

numerous accounts document various forms of mistreatment, including extortion at checkpoints and other reprehensible actions against innocent individuals (Chukwu et al., 2020).

For instance, the recent nationwide protests known as the SARS (Special Anti-Robbery Squad) serve as a stark reminder of police brutality. The issue of inadequate funding, among other factors, was highlighted as a key factor when protesters called for improved salaries and better equipment for police officers as essential components of police reform. This speculative link between poor funding and police misconduct is consistent with common theories that suggest a lack of resources can contribute to increased aggression (Evans & Cassells, 2014). In the case of the Nigerian Police, the use of excessive force or intimidation has been a way to compensate for the resources that the government has failed to provide, resulting in strained relationships with the citizens.

The problem of police brutality extends beyond international boundaries and is also prevalent within Sierra Leone itself. Sierra Leone has been grappling with the issue of police brutality for a significant period, with documented cases of violence and mistreatment by the police dating back to the colonial era, and to the time of the civil war (Bruce Baker, 2008). During the colonial periods, the Frontier Police, as it was then called, were trained to serve the interest of the colonial authorities, and not the people. Their loyalty and 'professional conduct' were precedents on directives from the colonial authority, irrespective of whether the actions were right or wrong, or violated civil liberties. There are reports about police personnel beating up chiefs for an allegation of disobedience to colonial mandates. During the war, the Sierra Leone Police (SLP) became a prime target for acts of violence, as individuals who had experienced police brutality sought retribution. Regrettably, this cycle of violence has persisted even in the post-war era, with frequent reports of police brutality and collusion with criminals (Bangura, I 2018).

The issue of police brutality in Sierra Leone has been widely criticized by various organizations and individuals for its severity. Despite the Sierra Leone government's efforts to reform the police force following the civil war, significant challenges persist, notably the lack of accountability for egregious crimes committed by the police. Reports of human rights violations by the Sierra Leone Police, such as physical assault and the unlawful killing of civilians in different regions of the country, are an ongoing concern.

The Sierra Leone Police (SLP) has faced allegations of employing excessive force, including the use of live ammunition, against civilians engaged in protests, resulting in casualties and property damage (Sierra Leone Telegraph, 2021). Incidents have been reported in various areas, such as Tombo, Lunsar, Makeni, and Hastings, where fatalities occurred during police operations, sparking public outcry and demands for accountability (Sierra Leone Telegraph, 2021). The SLP's tactics, such as the deployment of deadly weapons and indiscriminate firing, have been strongly criticized by human rights organizations like Amnesty International and the Centre for Accountability and Rule of Law (Bessem Ayuk, 2022). The Sierra Leone 2020 Human Rights Report also censured the police for their use of live ammunition against peaceful and unarmed demonstrators, a violation of International Humanitarian Law principles.

The issue of police brutality extends beyond the national level and is also prevalent in Bo City, one of Sierra Leone's largest cities. In August 2022, protests urging President Julius Maada Bio to step down turned violent, leading to the deaths of two individuals reportedly shot by the police, along with the killing of a security officer (Sierra Leone Telegraph, 2022). The government's handling of the demonstrations, which involved the suspension of the country's internet services and the military's assistance to the police force, has raised alarms regarding the excessive use of force and the erosion of civil liberties.

Within Bo City, one of Sierra Leone's most populous municipalities, incidents of police brutality have been observed not as isolated events but rather as recurring phenomena during protests, including those involving students and journalists. For instance, in Bo City, law enforcement officers resorted to gunfire against demonstrating students, leading to fatalities and injuries. Moreover, there have been reports of police

officers subjecting a journalist to brutal beatings, indicating a systematic pattern of violence and mistreatment within the police force (Sierra Leone Telegraph, 2021).

Drawing upon the contextual analysis presented above, it becomes apparent that police brutality holds significant consequences for the facilitation of peacebuilding processes. The prevalence of police brutality in Sierra Leone has posed a significant challenge to the country's peacebuilding efforts. The civil war, which came to a close in 2002, was characterized by unimaginable acts of brutality, including war crimes and widespread violations of human rights (Tony Karbo, 2012). In response to the conflict, Sierra Leone established the Truth and Reconciliation Commission (TRC) in 2004. The TRC's final report provided recommendations to address the systemic issues that contributed to the conflict, such as corruption, the urgent need for comprehensive reforms in the justice and security sectors, and the imperative of enhancing the democratic participation of youth and women (Tony Karbo, 2012).

Despite the ongoing efforts to improve human rights and the rule of law in Sierra Leone, police brutality remains a pressing issue. The country's security forces, notably the police, continue to face allegations of excessive force and human rights abuses, particularly directed towards marginalized groups and political adversaries. The enduring legacy of brutality has now triggered discussions for a change from the Sierra Leone Police Force to the Sierra Leone Police Service, a brand that many think will help change the narratives of policing in Sierra Leone.

4. Research Methodology

In reviewing the literature and discussing the variables contributing to the incidences of police brutality in Bo City, Sierra Leone, the study largely uses qualitative and quantitative research methodologies, drawing significantly from primary and secondary sources as well as other available pieces of literature. The research extensively utilizes various secondary data sources, such as newspapers, academic journal articles, and reports, to examine and elucidate the pervasive nature of violence committed by law enforcement officials. To obtain additional understanding of the issue, interviews were conducted with key members of the study population and certain police officials who preferred to remain anonymous.

5. Discussion

The prevalence of police brutality, both globally and locally, is commonly influenced by a variety of significant factors. Security experts often pinpoint issues such as police corruption, predatory behaviors within law enforcement, influence from political leaders and societal elites, as well as racial and tribal tensions, among other contributing elements (Pamela Chemelil, 2020). These factors have served as the driving force behind the ongoing presence of police brutality. Police departments worldwide have been accused of corruption, with reports of officers demanding bribes from individuals in exchange for turning a blind eye to breaches of peace (Pamela Chemelil, 2020).

This research highlights how violence conducted within the police department can perpetuate a culture of lawlessness, where officers believe they can act with impunity and escape accountability for their actions. This not only harms the victims of police brutality but also perpetuates a cycle of violence and abuse within the community. Ultimately, the results of this research underscore the urgent need for systemic reforms within Sierra Leone's law enforcement agencies to address issues of violence and ensure accountability and transparency in policing practices. Without addressing these root causes of police brutality, the cycle of abuse and impunity is likely to continue, further undermining the rule of law and the protection of human rights in the country.

The issue of police brutality in Sierra Leone is a complex one that has been an ongoing challenge. It is not an isolated phenomenon but rather a consequence of various situational and contextual factors that are inherent in the actual practice of policing. The research identified several factors that contribute to the occurrence of police brutality, including:

Lack of Training, Weak Oversight, and Accountability

The issue of police brutality in Sierra Leone, particularly in Bo City, is a pressing concern that has garnered significant attention in recent years (Concord Times, 2011). The problem is multifaceted, with several factors contributing to the excessive use of force by the police. One of the primary causes of police brutality is a lack of training and professionalism among police officers. The Sierra Leone Police (SLP) has been criticized for its handling of public uprisings and protests, with allegations of excessive force and human rights violations (Akwei, 2019). The use of teargas and the arrest of students and civilians during demonstrations have been condemned by organizations such as Amnesty International (Akwei, 2019). This lack of training and professionalism can lead to a culture of impunity, where officers feel they can engage in misconduct without consequences (Concord Times, 2011; Akwei, 2019).

Weak oversight and accountability are also significant factors in the perpetuation of police brutality in Sierra Leone. The SLP has been accused of using lethal weapons and random shootings at civilians, which goes against the principles of International Humanitarian Law (Sierra Leone Telegraph, 2021). The response to these incidents has been inadequate, with reports of police officers being suspended but not being held fully accountable for their actions. This lack of accountability can perpetuate a culture of brutality and human rights violations within the police force (Sierra Leone Telegraph, 2021; Concord Times, 2011).

The police are often not held accountable for their actions, and investigations into incidents of brutality are often slow or ineffective. This lack of accountability can lead to a culture of impunity, where police officers feel that they can act with impunity without fear of consequences. For example, in the case of the student protest in Bo, the police were accused of using excessive force, but the Inspector General of Police only confirmed the death and promised a thorough investigation, which did not seem to have led to any meaningful consequences for the officers involved (Akwei, 2019).

Furthermore, the police's handling of protests and demonstrations is often criticized for being heavy-handed and disproportionate. The police are accused of using tear gas and live bullets to disperse crowds, resulting in injuries and fatalities. This approach is not only illegal but also undermines the right to peaceful assembly and freedom of expression, which are fundamental human rights (Akwei, 2019; Amnesty International, 2018). In addition, the police's relationship with the public is often strained, with allegations of corruption and abuse of power being common. This can lead to a lack of trust and cooperation between the police and the community, making it more difficult to maintain law and order peacefully and professionally (Sierra Leone Telegraph, 2021).

The historical context of police brutality in Sierra Leone is also important to consider. The country's civil war and the subsequent peacebuilding efforts have led to a focus on community policing and the establishment of Local Policing Partnership Boards (LPPBs) (Albrecht, Olushegu et al., 2014). However, the effectiveness of these initiatives has been questioned, with concerns about the lack of clarity on the role of LPPBs and the scarcity of resources. This can lead to a situation where the police are not adequately equipped to handle public order situations, leading to the use of excessive force (Albrecht, Olushegu, et al., 2014).

In addition to these factors, the broader societal issues of corruption and clientelism within the SLP and the government can also contribute to police brutality (Sierra Leone Telegraph, 2021). The SLP has been accused of being influenced by political interests, leading to a lack of impartiality and professionalism in its operations. This can lead to a situation where the police are used to suppress political opponents and maintain the status quo rather than to protect the rights of all citizens (Sierra Leone Telegraph, 2021).

Corruption and Impunity within Law Enforcement Agencies

Allegations of corruption have plagued police institutions across the globe, with accusations of extorting money from individuals to evade legal consequences following breaches of public peace. Moreover, it has been observed that the police force often demands bribes to provide their services. The most distressing aspect, however, is the corruption of the police force by the political class and the societal elites, who exploit them to carry out acts of harassment and brutality against innocent citizens.

The study reveals that police corruption is not only prevalent but also deeply ingrained within the system. This widespread problem significantly hampers the SLP's ability to fulfill its constitutional objectives and erodes public trust. The root causes of police corruption are attributed to the abuse of power, discretionary decision-making, and a lack of adequate accountability mechanisms within the policing structure. The study further emphasizes that corruption enables unfair treatment of the public by the police, particularly when individuals refuse to engage in bribery.

The Sierra Leone Police (SLP) was established as an explicitly apolitical entity to maintain law and order in the country. The prevalence of corruption and impunity within law enforcement agencies in Sierra Leone, particularly in Bo City, presents significant challenges that subvert the rule of law and erode public trust in the institutions responsible for upholding order and safeguarding citizens (ACC, 2019). The Anti-Corruption Commission of Sierra Leone has identified various forms of corruption within the police force, including street-level bribery and extortion, bureaucratic corruption, organized crime, and political interference (ACC, 2019). These different forms of corruption not only undermine public trust but also foster an environment conducive to criminal activities and weaken the effectiveness of law enforcement efforts.

The prevalence of corruption within the police force is evident in the experiences of citizens who frequently encounter demands for bribes from police officers (Krönke, et al., 2024). Afrobarometer surveys indicate that only one-third of Africans believe their police force operates professionally and respects the rights of all citizens. Moreover, a significant number of individuals report instances of having to pay bribes in order to receive assistance or avoid problems (Krönke, et al., 2024). The perception of police corruption is closely associated with the low level of public trust in the police, dissatisfaction with government performance, and the prevailing sense of insecurity among citizens.

The Government of Sierra Leone has implemented a fresh national anti-corruption plan, incorporating regulations and statutes designed to enhance gender equality and combat corruption (GoSL UPR Midterm Report, 2019). Nevertheless, corruption continues to be a widespread problem within the police department, and the government encounters challenges in effectively tackling it due to the absence of transparency and accountability in the law enforcement agencies (Sierra Leone Human Rights Report, 2022).

Political Influence and Interference in Law Enforcement Operations

Political influence and interference in law enforcement operations are significant factors contributing to police brutality in Bo City and Sierra Leone. The presence of Local Policing Partnership Boards (LPPBs) in Sierra Leone, as highlighted in the DIIS report (2014), is intended to increase the level of interaction between the police and local communities, democratize security, and provide a policing model that is more inclusive and effective. However, the report also notes that the LPPBs face challenges, including a lack of clarity on their exact role, limited recordkeeping, and the fact that members may be driven by personal interests rather than solely by a desire to serve the community (DIIS Report, 2014). The LPPBs are seen as important for local safety and security, but their effectiveness is under scrutiny (DIIS Report, 2014). The report reveals that while the LPPBs are not political in the classical sense, they are not immune to political influence and interference. The fact that members who are openly politically active are present in the LPPBs suggests that political interests can influence the operations of these boards (DIIS Report, 2014). This political influence can lead to police brutality, as it can result in the prioritization of political interests over the needs of the community.

In Bo City, the implementation of community partnership policing, which involves vigilante organizations monitoring and protecting their neighborhoods, has been implemented to mitigate youth violence (Yusuf, M., 2023). However, this approach can also be influenced by political interests, leading to the potential for police brutality. The study on challenges in mitigating youth violence in Bo City highlights the absolute distrust in the police and the judiciary, which can be a result of political interference and influence (Yusuf, M., 2023).

The legacy of the Ugandan revolution has included a deeply rooted local democracy and a fear of national insecurity recurring, which can also contribute to political influence and interference in law enforcement

operations (Bruce Baker, 2004). This legacy can influence the way policing is carried out in Sierra Leone, leading to police brutality. In conclusion, political influence and interference in law enforcement operations are significant factors contributing to police brutality in Bo City and Sierra Leone. The presence of LPPBs, community partnership policing, and the legacy of the Ugandan revolution all play a role in shaping the policing landscape in Sierra Leone, and it is essential to address these factors to ensure that policing is carried out in a way that is fair, effective, and accountable to the community.

Race, Tribalism, and Religious Police Biasness

Throughout the globe, law enforcement agencies have frequently resorted to racial or tribal discrimination when employing violence against individuals. Extensive research and real-life encounters from various parts of the world have consistently portrayed a distressing image of police brutality towards black individuals in the Western world. Conversely, in Africa, the situation often assumes a tribal dimension, where members of specific tribal groups, distinct from the majority within the police force, become victims of violent actions. In the United States, empirical evidence has demonstrated that police violence predominantly revolves around racial factors, disproportionately affecting people of color. Numerous scholars have extensively documented the profound racial disparities in police brutality within the United States, with numerous studies revealing that black individuals frequently endure excessive and lethal force at the hands of law enforcement agencies (Desmond et al., 2016).

Research conducted in the United States revealed that the issue of police brutality targeting black individuals has escalated to a national level. The US Department of Justice has taken steps to ensure that law enforcement agencies are more proactive in upholding the law within the black community. It is widely believed that law enforcement officers tend to focus on afrocentric facial features when dealing with black suspects. Unfortunately, the investigations carried out by the Department of Justice have often overlooked the challenges faced by black Americans. Furthermore, the scrutiny of police departments has frequently been linked to racial profiling and biased sentencing practices (Chaney & Robertson, 2013).

The complex interplay of regionalism, tribalism, and religious factors contributes to police bias in Bo City and Sierra Leone. The general political discourse in Sierra Leone is characterized by hate messages and ethnoregional politics, which can lead to police brutality (Kormoh, J.L., 2020). The country's history of conflict and the ongoing political tensions between different ethnic groups can create an environment where police officers may be influenced by these divisions, leading to biased policing practices. The politicization of ethnic identities in Sierra Leone is a significant factor in shaping the country's political landscape and, by extension, the behavior of its law enforcement agencies (Kandeh, 1992). The affective attributes of ethnicity, such as kinship, common language, history, and culture, can create strong divisions between different ethnic groups, which can be exploited by politicians to gain power and influence. This can result in police officers being more likely to target certain ethnic groups, leading to police brutality.

The political discourse, the politicization of ethnic identities, the relations between people from different regions or districts, and the legacy of the civil war, all play a role in shaping the policing landscape in Sierra Leone, and it is essential to address these factors to ensure that policing is carried out in a way that is fair, effective, and accountable to the community.

Police Predatory Behavior and Inadequate Resources

Extensive research has consistently shown that the police service has frequently engaged in acts of violence against citizens without any external direction or influence. In such instances, the police have prioritized their interests and personal gains. This self-serving behavior, characterized by the use of violence by the police against citizens, is commonly referred to as police predatory behavior. A study conducted by Gerber and Mendelson (2008) highlighted that the police in Russia have predominantly acted independently when pursuing their interests. Regardless of ethnicity, political orientation, or social background, the police forces have played significant roles in implementing brutal counterinsurgency measures, solely to enhance their wealth and violently mistreat the citizens.

In Sudan, Mahmoud (2019) highlighted the state's use of police force to attack medical personnel. The government of Sudan (GoS) has consistently targeted doctors, making it clear that this is not an isolated incident but rather a deliberate policy. Following the civil unrest that began in December 2018, doctors have been subjected to police brutality while treating victims of violence, including those harmed by live ammunition and brutal assaults by police and state agents. Dozens of individuals are currently detained in unsanitary conditions.

The police force in Sierra Leone, particularly in Bo City, is known for its predatory behavior, which is exacerbated by inadequate resources (Burchert, 2013). This behavior is a significant concern, as it undermines the rule of law and contributes to a culture of corruption within the institution. The police are often seen as a means for personal enrichment rather than a force for public protection (Burchert, 2013). The predatory nature of the police is linked to the broader issue of corruption in Sierra Leone. The country has struggled with corruption, which has led to a situation where public officials, including those in the police force, engage in illegal activities to accumulate wealth (Burchert, 2013). This corruption is often fueled by a lack of adequate resources, including low salaries, which can lead to a culture of bribery and extortion (Burchert, 2013). Awoko Newspaper (2024) reports on a story where four police officers attached to the Bo West Police Station are currently under investigation for an alleged armed robbery at Taiama, a town in Moyamba District. This predatory behavior of police officers conniving with public offenders to rob people of their wealth for their interest is further echoed by YUSUF, M (2023), where personnel at the Bo West were arrested in Pujehun for armed robbery.

The situation in Bo City is particularly concerning, as it reflects a broader pattern of predatory behavior within the police force. This behavior is not limited to the police, as it is a symptom of a larger problem of corruption and inadequate governance in Sierra Leone (Burchert, 2013). The predatory behavior of the police in Bo City and Sierra Leone is a significant challenge to the country's efforts to build a stable and prosperous society. It undermines trust in the institution and contributes to a culture of fear and intimidation, which can have far-reaching consequences for the country's development (Burchert, 2013). In conclusion, the predatory behavior of the police in Bo City and Sierra Leone is a complex issue that is linked to broader problems of corruption and inadequate governance. Addressing this issue will require a comprehensive approach that includes improving the resources available to the police, increasing transparency and accountability, and promoting a culture of integrity within the institution.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The study concludes that police brutality incidents in Bo City reveal a troubling pattern of excessive force, abuse of power, and lack of accountability within the local law enforcement agencies. The data shows that a significant number of residents have experienced or witnessed instances of police brutality, ranging from physical violence to verbal abuse and harassment. These findings underscore the urgent need for a comprehensive review of police practices and policies in Bo City, as well as the implementation of reforms to ensure that law enforcement officers are held accountable for their actions.

The study's findings and conclusions have led to the formulation of recommendations aimed at enhancing the quality of professional services provided by the Sierra Leone Police (SLP). These recommendations also seek to foster active involvement from the government and other relevant parties in addressing and preventing police brutality.

- i. Governmental authorities and policymakers should prioritize investing in comprehensive training programs for police officers in Bo City and across Sierra Leone. This training should focus on human rights, conflict resolution, de-escalation techniques, and cultural sensitivity. By equipping police officers with the necessary skills and knowledge, they will be better prepared to handle challenging situations without resorting to violence.
- ii. It is crucial to strengthen the Police Partnership Board and the Complaint Discipline and Internal Investigations Department (CDIID) of the Sierra Leone Police and boost accountability mechanisms to address cases of police violence. This can be achieved by allowing the institutions responsible for

investigating complaints against police officers to do their work fairly, and without interference. This body should have the power to conduct impartial investigations, hold officers accountable for their actions, and recommend appropriate disciplinary measures or legal action when necessary.

- iii. Governmental authorities and policymakers should encourage the implementation of community policing initiatives in Bo City and across Sierra Leone. This approach involves building trust and collaboration between the police and the community they serve. By involving community members in decision-making processes and fostering open lines of communication, the police can better understand the needs and concerns of the community, reducing the likelihood of violence.
- iv. The SLP authorities should be transparent in their actions and decisions and hold officers accountable for any misconduct. This will help to build trust and confidence in the police force among the community. The study further recommends that, in order to effectively address and prevent police brutality in Bo City, it is imperative that concrete steps be taken to hold officers accountable for their actions. This may include implementing body cameras, establishing civilian oversight boards, and providing comprehensive training on de-escalation techniques and cultural sensitivity. Additionally, community members must be actively involved in the process of reforming law enforcement practices, as their input and perspectives are essential in creating a more just and equitable system.
- v. The study also recommends that it is essential for the Sierra Leone Police (SLP) to implement strict anti-corruption measures within the police force, such as regular integrity checks and disciplinary actions for those found guilty of corrupt practices. Additionally, all officers should receive training programs on human rights and ethical conduct to ensure they understand their responsibilities and the consequences of their actions. By promoting transparency and accountability, we can work towards building a more professional and trustworthy police force in Bo City.
- vi. Stakeholders should organize workshops and awareness campaigns to educate residents about their rights when interacting with the police. This will empower individuals to assert their rights and report any instances of police brutality or misconduct.

Conflict of Interests

The authors declare no conflict of interest in the publication of this paper.

References

1. ABDELMOTTLEP, Mamdooh A (2016) World Internal Security and Police Index 2016. Florida: International Police Science Association.
2. ABORISADE, R. & FAYEMI, J. (2015) Police Corruption in Nigeria: A Perspective on its Nature and Control. Nigerian Journal of Social Sciences, XVII (2): 245-262.
3. ACHPR (2022): ACHPR 71st OS: IHRDA statement on police brutality in Sierra Leone.
4. AKWESI, Ismail (2008). A Report on Police Violence in Bo City, Sierra Leone. Available online at <https://www.africanews.com/programmes/news/>
5. ALBRECHT, Peter, et al (2016): Community Policing in Sierra Leone – Local Policing Partnership Boards.
6. AMNESTY INTERNATIONAL (2014) Welcome to Hell Fire: Torture and Other Ill Treatment in Nigeria. London: Amnesty International Limited.
7. ARIHO, E. (2019). The role of Uganda police in, promotion of the right to life in Uganda from 1995 to 2018.
8. AWARENESS TIMES NEWSPAPER, (2017)
9. AYUK, Bessem (2022): ACHPR 71st OS: IHRDA statement on police brutality in Sierra Leone.
10. BAKER, Bruce (2004). Popular Justice and Policing from Bush to Democracy: Uganda 1981-2004. International Journal of the Sociology of Law 32: 333-348, DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijsl.2004.09.001>

11. BANGURA, I. (2018). Democratically Transformed or Business as Usual: The Sierra Leone Police and Democratic Policing in Sierra Leone. *Stability: International Journal of Security & Development*, 7(1).
12. BAYLEY, David, and ROBERT M. Perito. 2011. *Police Corruption: What Past Scandals Teach about Current Challenges*. USIP Special Report 294. Washington, DC: United States Institute of Peace.
13. CHANEY, C., & ROBERTSON, R. V. (2013). Racism and police brutality in America. *Journal of African American Studies*, 17(4), 480–505.
14. CHANEY, Cassandra & ROBERTSON, Ray V. (2013). *Racism and Police Brutality in America*. New York: Springer + Science Business Media. DOI: <https://10.1007/s12111-013-9246-5>
15. CHEMELIL, Pamela (2020): The Role of Police Brutality in Violent Conflict in the Capital Cities of East Africa: Case Study of Nairobi, Kenya.
16. CHUKWU, Christian Chima, SCENT, Grace A.-T. and EMERINWE, ObuzorMezewo (2020): Police brutality and human rights in Nigeria's democracy: Focus on restoration of man's dignity.7(15): 155-170. ISSN 2359-1412 [https://doi.org/10.21438/rbgas\(2020\)071512](https://doi.org/10.21438/rbgas(2020)071512).
17. COOPER, Hannah L. F. (2015). *War on Drugs Policing and Police Brutality*. Taylor & Francis
18. DESMOND, M., PAPACHRISTOS, A. V., & KIRK, D. S. (2016). Police violence and citizen crime reporting in the black community. *American Sociological Review*, 81(5), 857–876.
19. EVANS, G. W., & CASSELLS, R. C. (2014). Childhood poverty, cumulative risk exposure, and mental health in emerging adults. *Clinical Psychological Science*, 2(3), 287–296.
20. Gallagher, et al., eds, *The State of Policing in the United States*, Volume 1, supra note 645
21. GALLAGHER, Ryan et al (2023)
22. GERBER, T. P., & MENDELSON, S. E. (2008). Public experiences of police violence and corruption in contemporary Russia: a case of predatory policing? *Law & Society Review*, 42(1), 1– 44.
23. Human Rights Commission (2022). *Human Rights Commission of Sierra Leone Report*.
24. KANDEH, Jimmy D. (1992): *Politicization of Ethnic Identities in Sierra Leone*.
25. KARBO, Tony (2012). *LocalisingPeacebuilding in Sierra Leone: What Does It Mean?'* Conference Paper.
26. KIVOI, D. (2020). *Policing Reforms to Enhance Security in Kenya*. KIPPRA.
27. KORMOH, Joseph Lansana(2020): *Critically examining current trends in Sierra Leone's political landscape from the point of view of ethnoregional politics and hate messages*.
28. KRONKE, Matthias et al (2024). *Law Enforcers or Law Breakers: Beyond Corruption, Africans Cite Brutality and Lack of Professionalism among Police Failings*. Afrobarometer Policy Paper No. 90.
29. Mack T. (2014). The Mad and the Bad: The lethal use of force against Mad people by Toronto police. *Critical Disability Discourse*, 6, 7–52
30. MAHMOUD, O. (2019). The brutality of the Sudanese government against doctors is determined by policy rather than isolated events.
31. ONYANGO, G. (2018). *Police corruption: A phenomenological study on the transactional relationship between police and motorists at police stops in Kenya*.
32. Snyman, C (2008) *Criminal Law* 130-138; Also <http://www.saflii.org/za/journals/PER/2012/26.pdf> accessed April 28th, 2024.
33. THE SIERRA LEONE TELEGRAPH. (2022). *Three dead in Freetown as Sierra Leone is shut down by protesters calling for the resignation of President Bio*.
34. THOMPSON, B. L., & LEE, J. D. (2004). Who cares if police become violent? Explaining approval of police use of force using a national sample. *Sociological Inquiry*, 74(3), 381–410.
35. **UNITED NATIONS, (1979). Codes of Conduct for Law Enforcement Officials. Available at <https://garesolution34/169>**
36. YUSUF, Mohamed (2023): *Challenges in Mitigating Youth Violence in Bo City*, *Open Journal of Social Sciences*, 11, 418-428, ISSN Online: 2327-5960 ISSN Print: 2327-5952. <https://doi.org/10.4236/jss.2023.117029>.